

SCALING EFFECTS IN THE LOW VELOCITY IMPACT RESPONSE OF FIBRE METAL LAMINATES

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SUMMARY

This study focuses on assessing the possibility of using scale model tests for predicting the full-scale impact response of FMLs. The load-displacement traces were normalised and found to collapse onto a single curve suggesting that the laminates obey a scaling law. It was also shown that the failure modes and failure mechanisms were similar in all four scaled sizes.

Keywords: Impact test, hybrid materials, fibre metal laminate.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in investigating and understanding size effects in load-bearing engineering structures. For example, Jones [1] investigated scaling effects in a range of impact-loaded steel structures. Here, depending on the magnitude of the impact velocity and the scaling range, it was concluded that the rate sensitivity of the properties of steel could invalidate scaling laws. A number of studies have been undertaken in order to understand scaling effects in composite structures [2-4]. Wisnom [4] observed a size dependency when testing a carbon fibre reinforced plastic under four-point bending and in buckling. Kellas *et al* [2,3] used the Buckingham-Pi theorem to investigate scaling effects in the properties of a carbon fibre reinforced composite. Significant size effects were observed in the strength of the composites. Several workers have investigated scaling effects in the impact behaviour of composites [5,6]. Morton [6] studied scaling effects in the low velocity impact response of CFRP beams with different lay-ups and compared the experimental results with those obtained from a set of non-dimensional parameters obtained using the Buckingham Pi-theorem. It was observed that the impact duration scaled as the scale factor and the impact force as the scale factor squared. He also observed a significant decrease in laminate strength with increasing specimen size. Swanson [5] presented a summary of recent work from several scaling studies on CFRP where he used the Ritz procedure for predicting the response of composite plates and a Fourier series analysis for investigating the behaviour of cylinders. He noted that the strain values were independent of scaling size, whereas time varied linearly with the scale factor.

There is at present a strong interest in the use of fibre-metal laminates (FML's) in the design of lightweight aerospace structures. FMLs are hybrids based on combinations of composite materials such as glass fibre reinforced epoxy and metals such as aluminium alloy. Vlot [7] conducted low and high velocity impact tests on FMLs and compared their response to that offered by their constituent composites. He concluded that the damage zone in FMLs after impact is smaller than observed in plain composite. Reyes and Cantwell [8] conducted a study of high velocity impact tests on a series of novel sandwich structures and FML-reinforced aluminium foam based on thermoplastic matrices where different failure modes were identified.

The aim of the present paper is to investigate scaling effects in a novel fibre-metal laminate based on a polypropylene fibre reinforced polypropylene composite. It is hoped that the findings of this study will lead to a greater understanding of size effects in hybrid materials.

EXPERIMENTAL

The fibre-metal laminates (FMLs) investigated in this study were manufactured from aluminium alloy (type 2024-O) and a 0°/90° plain-woven self-reinforced polypropylene (SRPP) composite (Curv from Propex Fabrics). The term 'self-reinforced' refers to the fact that the composite is based on oriented polypropylene fibres embedded in a polypropylene matrix from the same material. A modified polypropylene film (Xiro 23.601-40 from Collano) was used as an adhesive in the FML to improve bonding between the aluminium and the SRPP, therefore avoiding the need to surface-treat the aluminium alloy. The FMLs were manufactured by stacking the composite, the interlayer material and the metal plies in a picture-frame mould and heating the stack to 165 °C in a Meyer hydraulic press before cooling slowly to room temperature. The processing temperature adopted here was sufficient to melt the polypropylene adhesive ($T_m = 145$ °C) without degrading the oriented polypropylene fibres in the SRPP. This manufacturing technique yielded high-quality panels exhibiting very little shrinkage in the composite plies.

Two approaches were employed to investigate stacking sequence effects in scaling the FMLs. In the first method, termed ply-level scaling, the laminate thickness was increased by scaling the thicknesses of plies in laminates based on the following stacking sequences $[Al_n, 0/90_n]_s$, where $n = 1, 2, 3$ and 4 corresponding to $1/4, 1/2, 3/4$ and full-scale respectively. The second method, known as sublaminates-level scaling, involved increasing the specimen thickness by repeating the basic sublaminates block n times. This procedure yielded laminates with stacking sequences of $[Al, 0/90]_{ns}$.

The low velocity impact response of a FML was studied using a falling-weight impact tower. Here, an impact carriage with attachable 5, 10, 15 and 20 mm diameter hemispherical noses were used for the four scaled sizes of FMLs, using a constant impact velocity of around 5.2 m/sec for all groups. A Kistler 5011 piezo-electric load cell located just above the impactor was used to measure the force-time history during the tests. Four different simple supported steel rings were constructed in order to keep the scaling proportionality as possible. Tests were conducted on an instrumented falling

weight impact tower. A laser-Doppler velocimeter was used to measure the velocity of the impactor during the impact event. The signal from the velocimeter was analysed using a BSI Flow software package by Dantec Measurement Technology. Combining the data from the piezo-electric load cell and the laser-Doppler velocimeter, force-displacement curves were obtained for each test.

The dimensions of the four samples were scaled in proportion as well as the simply support base and the four different impactors. The impact velocity was kept constant along the four scaled samples at approximately 5.2 m/s. Table 1 shows the four different scaled dimensions for the samples, the hemispherical impactors and supports used for the analysis. In order to maintain the scaling proportionality [1], the impact masses used in this study were scaled to the cubic to maintain a linear response with the scaled volume samples. Tables 2 and 3 show the impact masses used for the different scaled samples as well as the impact forces and energies. After testing, samples were analyzed by eye to identify any indentation damage on the front surface and distal side of the impacted area. Then, the samples were cut in half across the impacted zone and polished for further internal analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1a shows typical force-displacement traces following impact on the four scale sizes at a constant impact energy of $302n^3$ Joules. From the figure, it is evident that the panels exhibit some recovery at the end of the test, indicative of an elastic response in the aluminum and composite plies. It is worth noting that none of these specimens showed external damage after the impact test. The residual displacement in the figure is therefore due to plastic deformation in the metal and composite plies. The load-displacement trace for the largest ($n=1$) sample exhibits some initial oscillatory behavior due to ringing in the load cell.

Previous work on scaling the low velocity impact behavior of composites has shown that the impact force should scale as n^2 and the resulting plate deflection as n [1]. Scaling effects in the force-displacement traces were therefore investigated by dividing the impact force by the square of the corresponding scale size, (F/n^2) , and the impact displacement by the scale size, (Δ/n) . Figure 1b shows the resulting normalized force-displacement curves for the ply level samples shown in Figure 1a. An examination of the figure indicates that all of the normalized traces are very similar in appearance, collapsing onto what appears to be a single unique trace, suggesting that the FMLs obey a simple scaling law. Similar trends were observed in the traces of the samples scaled at a sublaminar level.

Figure 1. Impact force vs. displacement traces for scaled samples struck by a hemispherical impactor and b) Normalized impact force vs. displacement traces. Energy = $302n^3$ Joules.

Figure 2. Normalised maximum force vs. scale size for the two stacking configurations.

The cross-sections of samples subjected to an impact energy of $403n^3$ Joules, scaled using both techniques are presented in Figure 3. Here, the incident energy was sufficient to just generate lower surface fracture of the aluminum layer in the FMLs. An examination of the photograph in Figure 3a indicates that the level of plastic deformation is similar for all four scale sizes. All samples exhibit localised denting and thinning around the point of impact and permanent deformation, with fracture in the lowermost aluminum layer. Delamination between the composite plies as well as debonding at the aluminum-composite interface were apparent at all scale sizes. In addition, whitening of the interfacial adhesive layers due to localized shear was observed in all specimens away from the point of impact. Shear failure was observed

close to the point of impact, visible in the lowermost aluminum layer, exhibiting a typical 45° fracture.

Figure 3. Cross-sections of scaled samples following an impact energy of $403n^3$ Joules. Samples scaled at: a) a ply-level and b) a sublaminar-level.

Figure 4. FML plates scaled at sublaminar-level following low velocity impact at an energy of $403n^3$ Joules.

Photos of sublaminar-scaled plates subjected to an impact energy of $403n^3$ Joules are shown in Figure 4, where damage resulting from low velocity impact tests can be clearly seen.

Figure 5 shows the normalized values of the perforation energy for the two types of FML target. The perforation energy (E_p) is compared to the predicted perforation energy (E_{pp}) calculated from the smallest scale sample. From the figure it is clear that

the perforation energy scales with the scale size with the value for the full-scale plate being similar to that of its 1/4 scale counterpart.

Figure 5. Ratio of the perforation energy (E_p) and the corresponding predicted value (E_{pp}) versus the scaling size.

Figure 6 shows the normalization values of the impact duration. The impact durations (t_0) are divided by the predicted durations (t_{0p}) calculated from the smallest scale sample. Here, the two stacking arrangements are compared, i.e. those associated with ply-level and the sublaminates-level scaling, where only small differences are observed. An examination of the figure indicates that the contact duration is slightly shorter in the larger samples although this may be a result of experimental scatter.

Figure 6. Normalized values of time for ply-level and sublaminates-level scaling.

The low velocity impact response of these multi-layered plates was further investigated using the non-dimensional approach developed by Wen and Jones. Here, it was shown that a plot of the non-dimensional target deflection, δ , (defined as the residual

displacement following impact, Δ , divided by the thickness of the sample, h) against the non-dimensional impact energy, χ , should yield a common curve over the range of scale sizes considered. The non-dimensional energy is defined as:

$$\chi = \frac{E}{\sigma_y d^3}$$

where E is the impact energy, σ_y is the yield stress at scale size n and d is a characteristic scale length, chosen in this case to be the indenter diameter.

Figures 7a and 7b show plots of non-dimensional permanent deflection (δ) versus non-dimensional impact energy (χ) for specimens scaled using both the ply-level and the sublaminar-level approaches. An examination of the figures indicates that both sets of data appear to exhibit unique trends with the data collapsing on to straight lines. It is interesting to note that the slope of both traces are almost identical, suggesting that both sets of laminates exhibit a very similar response. The evidence in Figure 7 again supports the conclusion that the FML plates obey a simple scaling law.

Figure 7. Variation of the non-dimensional permanent deflection with non-dimensional impact energy following low velocity impact tests on FMLs scaled at: a) a ply-level and b) a sublaminar-level.

CONCLUSIONS

Low velocity impact tests on fibre metal laminates based on aluminium plies and sheets of self-reinforced polypropylene have shown that the drop-weight impact behaviour of these hybrids follows a simple scaling law. It has been shown that key parameters such as the maximum impact force and the perforation energy scale with size. Damage in the FML plates under low velocity impact testing followed a similar pattern for all scale sizes as the impact energy was increased. Damage was characterised, as a function of increasing impact energy, by failure of the aluminium alloy on the distal side at the threshold energy level, leading up to failure of both the aluminium alloy on the proximal side and fibre failure in the SRPP at the perforation energy.

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Table 1. Dimensions of the four different scaled specimens for low impact test.

Scale size	Ply-level thickness (mm)	Sublamine thickness (mm)	Circular support inner diameter (mm)	Sample volume (times)	Impactor diam. (mm)
1/4	1.77	1.77	50	1	5
1/2	3.51	3.62	100	7.93	10
3/4	5.45	5.44	150	27.71	15
Full scale	7.03	7.24	200	63.54	20

Table 2. Values of the four different scaled specimens for low impact test at ply-level.

Scale size	Cubic factor	Masses kg	Force (N)	Impact energy (Joules)	Specific perforation energy (Jm ² /kg)
1/4	1	0.35	2139	4.7	1.3
1/2	8	2.81	9349	37.5	5.5
3/4	27	9.47	17630	128	11.6
Full scale	64	22.46	29584	302.5	21.5

Table 3. Values of the four different scaled specimens for low impact test at sublamine-level.

Scale size	Cubic factor	Masses kg	Force (N)	Impact energy (Joules)	Specific perforation energy (Jm ² /kg)
1/4	1	0.35	2139	4.7	1.3
1/2	8	2.81	9774	38.3	5.5
3/4	27	9.47	17956	127.3	11.8
Full scale	64	22.46	31714	301.9	21.2